

SYSTEMS ANALYSIS IN PRACTICAL PUBLIC HEALTH ON THE EXAMPLE OF MANAGING PATIENTS WITH CHEMICAL EYE BURNS

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Relevance. Systems analysis is associated with a complex set of elements interacting with each other. The result of a system analysis is a comparative description of alternative options in order to select the most optimal one, in terms of all compared parameters, and at the same time, the least expensive one, which is especially important in the context of insurance medicine. During the period of capitalization of the country, and especially during the period of transition to insurance medicine, the calculation of the economic efficiency of the introduction of new methods of treatment and the calculation of the cost of treatment in general is a very important socio-economic factor.

Purpose: To optimize approaches to the treatment of patients with chemical eye burns based on an individualized approach to the treatment management, therapy, prediction of complications and outcomes of chemical eye burns.

Methods and techniques. The following categories were identified as alternative options (A): A1 - standardized approach, without individualization of patients with their management according to the National Protocol as the lesion manifests itself and in the dynamics of the development of complications of the process; A2 - individualized approach based on the use of genetic analysis based on HLA testing; A3 - individualized approach based on the determination of FA in patients. The next step was the selection of criteria (K), by which the effectiveness of each of the proposed alternative approaches and its implementation will be evaluated: K - the quality of care for patients. This criterion was evaluated according to the following indicators: K1 - the duration of the main manifestations of the disease (in weeks); K2 - the effectiveness of the therapy (the frequency of complications and relapses); K3 - the degree of restoration of the organ of vision after a chemical burn of the eyes (according to visual acuity);

When choosing criteria, we limited ourselves to the most significant of them, which can show the effectiveness of each of the selected alternative approaches to managing patients with chemical eye burns.

Results. The next stage of the analysis was to evaluate the effectiveness of each of the compared approaches to managing patients based on the possibilities of their implementation and the greatest economic efficiency. In this regard, in the work, scaling was carried out according to the specified criteria, with an assessment of their economic significance and

limitations in their application. According to the developed criteria K (K1, K2, K3), probability scales (S) were formed. Probabilities were assessed on a scale from 0.0 to 1.0. In this regard, the developed scales for assessing the most optimal approach to the management of patients with chemical eye burns present options from 0.0 to 1.0, taking into account the proposed option with the definition of FA and each of the alternative methods of comparison: a standardized approach and individualized testing for HLA histocompatibility (A3, A1 and A2 respectively). At the next stage, we calculated the probabilities according to the specified criteria for each of the alternative options. The probabilities (S) were calculated according to the following formula: $A_i = \sum_i^n \times S_i / n \times (1-R_{ij})$

According to systems analysis the larger the value of S, the more effective the proposed method for solving the problem. Based on the foregoing, alternatives A2 and A3 - an individualized approach to therapy are more preferable compared to the standardized method of managing patients with a chemical eye burn $SA_2 = 0.83 > SA_1 = 0.43$; $SA_3 = 0.83 > SA_1 = 0.43$. And taking into account the fact that the approach to managing patients with chemical burns of the eyes with their individualization using the method based on HLA testing is more costly (from 500,000 UZ soums according to the tariff) than the method of determining FA we propose (87,000 UZ soums according to the tariff), then despite their similar efficacy, an individualized approach based on testing patients for their acetylation status should be used.

Conclusion. Thus, based on the results of calculating the economic efficiency, as well as using a systemic morphological analysis of alternative options, it was found that the use of an individualized approach to the management of patients with chemical eye burns by determining their acetylation phenotype can not only reduce the economic costs of treating such patients, but also improve the quality of care for people with chemical eye burns by reducing the frequency of relapses and complications of the disease, the length of stay of patients in the hospital and the best restoration of the functional state of the organ of vision.

References. According to the results of a systematic morphological analysis of alternative options, it was found that the application of an individualized approach to the treatment management of patients with chemical eye burns by determining their acetylation phenotype can not only reduce the economic costs of treating such patients, but also improve the quality of care for people with chemical eye burns, by reducing the frequency of relapses and complications of the disease, the length of stay of patients in the hospital and the best restoration of the functional state of the organ of vision.